

Interview Royal Air Force Museum – Darren Priday
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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys.

- Presentation of the institution:

The Royal Air Force Museum was opened in 1972 in Hendon, near London, in honor of the RAF's fiftieth anniversary. Since 1979, the RAF Museum has also managed the Cosford Aerospace Museum in Cosford (opened in 1972) on behalf of the Ministry of Defense. In 1998, the museums merged to become one institution, one being renamed RAF Museum London and the other RAF Museum Midlands. The conservation center (Michael Beetham Conservation Centre, MBCC) is located in Cosford.

The purpose of the organization is to share the story of the Royal Air Force, past, present and future – using the stories of its people and our collections in order to engage, inspire and encourage learning.

Source : <https://www.rafmuseum.org.uk/about-us/default/>, accessed 18.06.21

- The operating chain: from wreck to museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved? Defining a recovery project? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing? What is their approach? Is the approach similar or not in the case of projects that are different?

In the UK, the Ministry of Defense is responsible for the investigation of all military aircraft crash sites.

The RAF Museum has been involved in several wreck salvage operations in the past (such as the Halifax Mk II recovered in 1973 from Lake Hoklingen in Norway and the Hurricane Mk I retrieved from the Thames Estuary in the same year). The museum also has experience with stabilization, reassembly and exhibition of immersed aircraft.

The Dornier Do 17 Z – 2 is the biggest recovery of its kind in British waters.

The wreck was located in Goodwin Sands (near Ramsgate) by a fisherman, and later on location was confirmed by divers in 2008. The wreck's identity was confirmed after sonar scans were conducted jointly by the museum, Wessex Archaeology and the Port of London Authority. A license was able to be issued for the recovery of the aircraft as it was not a war grave (there was no body in the aircraft).

The recovery of the Dornier was a complex project, which needed to be conducted within a limited timeframe because of weather and tide conditions. The project was managed by the RAF museum, but in close collaboration with a group of experts and stakeholders, including scientists, divers, funders and donors.

The following institutions were partners & stakeholders in the project:

The Royal Air Force Museum – Project Manager

Seatech – Dive Team

NHMF – Funders

WarGaming.Net – Donors

EADS - Donors

Port of London Authority – On water assistance

Imperial College - Conservation Consultants/Advisers

Parallel to the plan for the recovery itself, the project also included also planning for post-recovery treatment, as well as for appropriate funding to ensure the project was viable.

The initial plan was to have a custom-made frame adjusted to the wreck for the lifting, but due to bad weather and delays in the operations the plan had to be changed. The RAF Museum instructed the lifting company to attach lifting equipment to specific points on the aircraft, identified as the strongest. After recovery, the aircraft was put on a barge and disassembled into 2 halves before transport to the conservation center in Cosford.

- Concept of "conservation": Do you think of the long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle? How do you define long term? What does the idea of "conservation" mean to you for this kind of heritage? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution?

Conservation techniques have advanced greatly in the last 40 years. Similar restoration efforts undertaken in Norway and Australia in the past few years offer the prospect of less intrusive methods for stabilizing and preserving aircraft structures immersed in salt or fresh water for extended periods

- Who works on these collections (after recovery): conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), or volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people directly in charge of interventions? (addition to Form A)

MBCC has two conservation teams: 1 for larger objects, including aircraft, and 1 for smaller objects. In the larger objects team, all staff have a technical background: 8 people are former Air Force and 1 is a painter. Darren Friday, Conservation manager, is a former Air Force engineer.

Additionally, 50 to 55 regular volunteers may participate in different operations.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact: aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A)?

The RAF Museum has a non-flying collection. Collection management approach ranges from Conservation (keep as it is), Restoration (minimal but necessary interventions) to Renovation (significant interventions and remaking for historical representation).

Currently, the Dornier is kept in Cosford. The intention is to reassemble this aircraft and display it in an “archeological state” showing its history, and build a custom-made enclosure for it.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage): rooms or hall? awareness about influence of climate on preservation? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and changes to them over the year (addition to Form A)?

The museum is aware of the importance of regulating climate, but at the moment the exhibition spaces and storage spaces have no climate control, and no pollutant control.

- Reflecting on their own practice: do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefact? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field? Has your practice evolved through those connections?

The project for the Dornier was an incredibly thorough project for the RAF museum. The goal from the start was to work with scientists (from Imperial College London) to design a specific treatment for this specific wreck.

Darren is involved in a small, informal group of museums and conservators with similar interests. They organized a seminar on museum non-flying aircraft restoration in 2020 in Helsinki.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems)? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant)? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A)?

The aircraft wreck was still in structurally good condition when recovered, largely intact, to some extent unexpectedly (the main under carriage tyres were still inflated). The wreck had suffered from effects of sea life (build-up of marine concretions) and surface abrasion from the sand on the seabed.

The treatment protocol was designed by Imperial College London, with the aim of helping to dissolve marine concretions and treat corrosion.

The treatment protocol was applied to wings and fuselage. It included:

- sheltering the aircraft wreck during treatment: 2 custom-built hydration polytunnels, placed outdoors at MBCC. Polytunnels were equipped with a system of spray nozzles.
- spraying the wreck, with a low concentration citric acid-based solution. Spraying lasted for 18 months, acidic solution being sprayed for 10 minutes out of every 30. Automatic spraying was reinforced by manual spraying.
- localized removal of debris using plastic scrapers
- in September 2014, the acid solution spraying was stopped, and the wreck underwent an intense wash down, before being moved into the conservation center.

The treatment helped remove marine growth and corrosion products of both ferrous and aluminium parts. Battle-related damage (bullet and shrapnel holes) became more visible, as well as small areas of the original paint finish.

The main airframe could also undergo partial reconstruction to reinforce fragile areas. Parts that needed reconstruction were identified based on drawings supplied by the European Aeronautical Defense and Space company (EADS).

Smaller components (such as an engine valve, empty bullet cases, a tube from the flying controls, sprocket and roller chain) were treated separately using over treatment methods. The main action was to remove marine concretions, the materials were found to be in very good condition underneath (very little corrosion observed). After treatment, the surface was protected by coating the items in a layer of Renaissance Wax® or a two-part clear paint product.

By trialing various conservation methods employed regularly in museums, the Conservation team can identify those processes most applicable to metals which have been subject to long periods underwater.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history?

The Dornier Do 17 is a historic Second World War German Bomber, the last surviving of its type, strongly connected with the Battle of Britain. This episode of WWII is very important for the UK, as it was a major, harsh military campaign, considered a pivotal moment in the UK's history.

Quote from Air Vice-Marshal Peter Dye, Director General of the RAF Museum 2010-2014: "The discovery and recovery of the Dornier is of national and international importance. The aircraft is a unique and unprecedented survivor from The Battle of Britain and the Blitz. It will provide an evocative and moving exhibit that will allow the Museum to present the wider story of the Battle of Britain and highlight the sacrifices made by the young men of both air forces and from many nations. It is a project that has reconciliation and remembrance at its heart."

Initially, it was planned to display the Dornier wreck in London, in a newly designed hall for the Battle of Britain. As the aircraft proved to be too fragile for transport, it will be kept at Cosford. The new goal is to build a specific hall for it there. Some of the smaller components are already on display at Cosford (e.g., one of the engines).